

FORTY-FIFTH ANNUAL SYMPOSIUM ON FREQUENCY CONTROL
**HYDROGEN MASER PERFORMANCE AT THE UNITED STATES NAVAL OBSERVATORY
AND THE NAVAL RESEARCH LABORATORY**

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Abstract

The United States Naval Observatory(USNO) has been using hydrogen masers for over six years as part of the USNO Master Clock. The Naval Research Laboratory(NRL) has also been using masers references as part of the NRL Clock testing facility since September 1985. The masers reported on in this paper will include the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory VLG-11, VLG-12 and masers from the Sigma Tau Standards Corporation. This paper will describe the operation of the masers at USNO and NRL including stability, aging rates, and reliability.

Introduction

The United States Naval Observatory(USNO) is responsible for time keeping within the Department of Defense(DOD). The USNO Master Clock is a system of several hydrogen masers, cesium beam and mercury ion frequency standards. USNO has up-graded its time scale and in recent years has added an NRL designed 48 channel long term clock measurement system[1], a new full Kalman filter based clock ensemble[2], three trapped Mercury Ion devices[3] and fourteen Hydrogen masers[4, 5].

NRL has been in the forefront of advanced clock development for a variety of DOD systems including the USNO Master Clock upgrade program and the Global Positioning System (GPS) atomic clock development program[6]. Hydrogen masers serve as the primary frequency standard in the NRL clock test facility. Starting from the early 1970's NRL purchased four SAO VLG series masers and two Sigma Tau masers to use as references. The two Sigma Tau masers (NRL-N1 and NRL-N2) and one of the SAO VLG-11 (P-12) series masers were chosen to make up NRL's primary frequency reference ensemble with the other three SAO VLG series masers, including the original VLG-10 P-0, are located at other test sites.

Performance of USNO masers

The new USNO long term clock measurement system was designed to take data in a highly automated fashion, and has proved to be ideal for measurement of a large number of clocks over very long periods of time. This 48 channel dual-mixer system records data every hour with a measurement noise of less than five picoseconds. The computers running the measurement software are available over an ethernet type UNIX network, which makes data handling very easy.

At present USNO is operating twelve Hydrogen Masers with two more expected to arrive later in 1991. Of the twelve masers already at USNO, two are SAO VLG-11 series masers (P-18 and P-19), four are SAO VLG-12 (P-22, 23, 24 and P-25) series masers and six are Sigma Tau masers (N1, N2, N3, N4, N5 and N6). Data on two of the Sigma Tau masers, N1 and N6 was not available for this paper because they have been sent to other USNO sites.

The performance of eight of the USNO masers taken over a period of 264 days was measured against the USNO Master Clock. This 264 day span covers MJD 48104 to MJD 48368 (August 1990 - April 1991). The drift removed frequency stability of each combination of clock pairs was then calculated and used in an N-Cornered hat estimation[7, 8], so the true stability of each clock could be found. Table 1 shows the N-Corner Hat estimates of the frequency stability of the USNO masers. Masers denoted as P are built by SAO and masers with a N prefix were built by Sigma Tau. During a one month period starting in March 1991 P-23 exhibited a 8×10^{-15} frequency shift which distorts the stability numbers for this clock.

N2, and P18 are being steered to the USNO Master Clock by use of the high resolution synthesizer built into both types of masers. Because of this, only a shorter span of data was available for the calculation of the stability of masers N2 and

N-CORNER HAT FOR A 263 DAY PERIOD COVERING MJD(8104-8367) WITH DRIFT REMOVED.

	1 DAY	2 DAY	4 DAY	8 DAY	16 DAY	32 DAY
N3	1.4	1.5	2.0	2.7	3.8	5.7
N4	1.6	2.1	2.7	3.4	4.9	5.6
N5	1.2	0.85	.75	0.8	0.73	0.9
P19	1.95	2.0	2.05	1.8	1.9	2.2
P22	3.1	3.6	4.4	4.8	6.2	8.7
P23*	5.7	6.9	9.0	11.6	13.0	14.5
P24	0.6	0.97	0.82	0.92	1.05	1.2
P25	1.2	1.4	1.83	3.3	5.49	7.5
N2	1.1	1.36	1.24	2.3		
P18	1.9	2.4	2.7	2.8		

NOTE: All values are times 1×10^{-15}
 *8 $\times 10^{-14}$ frequency shift greatly influenced data on P-23

P18. The steer amounts were removed from the data and a 3-Corner hat estimate was calculated. This data is also shown in Table 1.

The drift rate was removed by using a simple linear fit to the frequency data which worked well for most pairs of clocks. P-25 had a logarithmic shape to its frequency drift, with the drift rate slowing by almost 50 %. Drift rates for each clocks are shown below versus BIPM.

- N3 - BIPM NONE
- N4 - BIPM NONE
- N5 - BIPM $+0.25 \times 10^{-15}/\text{DAY}$
- P18 - BIPM $+0.29 \times 10^{-15}/\text{DAY}$
- P23 - BIPM $+0.99 \times 10^{-15}/\text{DAY}$
- P19 - BIPM $+1.09 \times 10^{-15}/\text{DAY}$
- N2 - BIPM $+1.26 \times 10^{-15}/\text{DAY}$
- P24 - BIPM $+1.82 \times 10^{-15}/\text{DAY}$
- P22 - BIPM $+2.81 \times 10^{-15}/\text{DAY}$
- P25 - BIPM $+3.37 \times 10^{-15}/\text{DAY}$

NOTE: NONE IS $< (+/-) 1 \times 10^{-16}/\text{DAY DRIFT}$

PERFORMANCE OF NRL MASERS

The Sigma Tau corporation delivered two Hydrogen masers (NRL-N1 and NRL-N2) to NRL in the September 1985. These masers have been in almost continuous operation since the day they arrived having been shut off only once because of dead back-up batteries. No adjustments have been made to any of the masers settings for almost six years.

NRL and USNO installed a cesium clock at a local television station (WTTG channel 5) that is used to produce the 77 Mhz carrier frequency of this station[9]. Both NRL and USNO mix their local references with the received television carrier to produce a 2250 Hz beat frequency. USNO feeds their beat frequency to NRL over a dedicated telephone line and NRL compares the phase of these two 2250 Hz signals. The cesium clock at WTTG will cancel, and NRL is left with the phase difference between NRL-reference (NRL-N1) and the USNO Master Clock. The short term noise in this method is good but signal drop outs can cause phase breaks to occur.

Using this television carrier phase comparison system to measure the long term frequency drift in the NRL reference shows that NRL-N1 had a drift rate of less than $5 \times 10^{-17}/\text{day}$ for almost six years versus BIPM.

NRL-N2 exhibited a non-linear frequency drift rate during the first two and half years of operation at NRL, with the drift rate slowly increasing. This drift rate changed to a constant rate of $+4 \times 10^{-15}/\text{day}$ for the next two years. Approximately one year ago the drift rate shifted again to a constant rate $+3.5 \times 10^{-15}/\text{day}$ and remained at that rate.

The drift removed frequency stability of NRL-N1 versus NRL-N2 is shown below. Because these two clock are similar one may assume that one of the two clocks are at least the square root of two better than shown in below. NRL-N1 versus BIPM stability estimates for 100 day and 200 day

sample times are also shown below.

TYPICAL FREQUENCY STABILITY NRL-N1 VERSUS NRL-N2 (DRIFT REMOVED)

1 sec	2.5×10^{-13}
10 sec	3.5×10^{-14}
100 sec	6.0×10^{-15}
1 hour	5.0×10^{-15}
2 hour	4.8×10^{-15}
4 hour	4.6×10^{-15}
8 hour	3.6×10^{-15}
1 day	2.8×10^{-15}
2 day	2.1×10^{-15}
5 day	1.2×10^{-15}
10 day	1.2×10^{-15}

FREQUENCY STABILITY ESTIMATE OF NRL- N1 VERSUS BIPM (NOT DRIFT REMOVED)

100 day	4.7×10^{-15}
200 day	5.6×10^{-15}

RELIABILITY

The reliability of both the VLG-12 and Sigma Tau masers has been excellent. The only systematic problem was in the older SAO VLG-11 series maser's vacuum system. The VLG-11 masers require replacement of the ion pump every two or three years. The SAO VLG-12 series masers high vacuum ion pump system is improved and should last much longer. Also several VLG-11 masers have suffered receiver failures due to an amplifier chip running hot and burning out. This design error has been corrected and all of USNO masers have been modified to correct this error.

All of the USNO Sigma Tau masers needed their quartz oscillators replaced. After consulting the company that manufactures this quartz oscillator, a design flaw was discovered. The company changed their design and future problems are not expected. It is expected that the useful lifetimes of both the VLG-12 and Sigma Tau masers will be greater than 12 years.

CONCLUSION

The USNO clocks with the best frequency stability over the time period reported on in this paper were N5, P19 and P24. N5 and P24 long term drift removed frequency stability at 32 day sample times were less than 1.2×10^{-15} and the stability of P-19 was 2.2×10^{-15} .

The clocks with the least drift were N3, N4, N5 and P18. These drift rates were less than 3.0×10^{-16} /DAY versus BIPM. Over a period of less than one year measuring drift rates smaller than this is very difficult because of measurement uncertainties between BIPM and USNO.

NRL master frequency reference NRL-N1 has shown a net long term frequency drift versus BIPM of less than 5×10^{-17} /day over a six year period.

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